

LEVEL OF TEACHER'S MOTIVATION TOWARDS PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT ACROSS GENERATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the level of a teacher's motivation towards professional development across generations. It sought to answer the following questions the profile of the respondents as to generations, the motivational level of teachers towards professional development across generations (Generation Z or iGen, Generation Y (millennials), Generation X and Baby Boomers) in terms of the following factors: Content Focused; Active Learning; Task Collaboration; Effective Practices; Learning Support; Reflective Outlook and Sustainable Plan. The significant difference in the level of motivation towards professional development of the generations (Generation Z or Gen Z, (millennials) Generation Y, Generation X, and Baby Boomers) in terms of the following factors: Content Focused and Active Learning; Task Collaboration and Effective Practices; Learning Support and Reflective Outlook and Sustainable Plan. The program intervention could be proposed to motivate teachers to upgrade themselves toward professional development. Based on the findings as summarized, the following conclusions were drawn: Teachers were from Generation X 1965-1980 and Generation Y (millennials). The level of teachers' motivation across generations in Content-Focus, Active Learning, Task Collaboration, Effective Practices, Learning Support, Reflective Outlook, and Sustainable Plan were all well-motivated. There is a significant difference in the level of motivation towards professional development of the generations with Generation Z vs. Baby Boomers and Generation Y vs. Baby Boomers therefore the hypothesis is rejected. The researcher proposed a program intervention to motivate teachers to upgrade themselves toward professional development.

Keywords: *Keyword Teacher's motivation, professional, development, across generations*

INTRODUCTION

The most valuable resource in the educational system is the teacher. Professional development for educators is becoming more and more important as a means of assisting pupils in acquiring the increasingly sophisticated abilities necessary for success in the twenty-first century. Effective professional development (PD) is therefore necessary to assist educators in acquiring and honing the teaching techniques necessary to impart these skills.

Professional growth is necessary to promote and maintain progress in any field of professional activity. In order for students to develop more complex skills, they must thrive in the twenty-first century, at the same time that professional development for instructors is gaining popularity. Sophisticated teaching techniques are needed to develop student competencies like critical thinking, in-depth comprehension of challenging subject, complex problem solving, effective communication and teamwork, and self-direction. Consequently, in order to impart these talents, teachers need to acquire and refine the teaching strategies, which necessitates efficient professional development (PD). However, research indicates that a large number of professional development programs do not appear to be assisting in the modification of teaching practices or student learning. In light of this, the goal was to pinpoint the traits of effective professional development.

A number of increasingly complicated tasks, duties, and competencies in the teaching profession have become necessary in the twenty-first century due to the rise in educational expectations. One of the key factors in the performance of the institutions is the motivation level and generational disparities of teachers, who are the most strategic factor in educational efficacy (Akar, 2020).

Professional development is very important nowadays. Teachers are not only teachers. In lieu, the researcher believes that through this study, it would provide more awareness and deeper understanding of different challenges and perspectives of teachers from different generations. This study would help people understand their views on their current perspective on professional development. This study is seen to be beneficial not only for the teachers, learners, school heads, but as well as for the development of learning and quality education.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the level of a teacher's motivation towards professional development across generations. It sought to answer the following questions;

1. What is the profile of the respondents as to generations?

2. What is the motivational level of teachers towards professional development across generations (Generation Z or iGen, Generation Y (millennials), Generation X and Baby Boomers) in terms of the following factors:
 - 2.1 Content Focused;
 - 2.2 Active Learning;
 - 2.3 Task Collaboration;
 - 2.4 Effective Practices;
 - 2.5 Learning Support;
 - 2.6 Reflective Outlook;
 - 2.7 Sustainable Plan?
 3. Is there a significant difference in the level of motivation towards professional development of the generations (Generation Z or Gen Z, (millennials) Generation Y, Generation X, and Baby Boomers) in terms of the following factors:
 - 3.1 Content Focused and Active Learning;
 - 3.2 Task Collaboration and Effective Practices;
 - 3.3 Learning Support and Reflective Outlook;
 - 3.4 Sustainable Plan?
 4. What program intervention could be proposed to motivate teachers to upgrade themselves toward professional development?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed quantitative descriptive research design. This is suited to this type of research since it aims to measure and determine teachers' motivation toward professional development and its relationship to other variables. The goal of quantitative research is to quantify the process of gathering and analyzing data. It originated from a deductive method influenced by positivism and empiricist ideologies, which prioritized testing theories (Wikipedia). This research technique, which is related to the social, formal, applied, and natural sciences, encourages the objective empirical investigation of observable phenomena in order to test and comprehend correlations. This is accomplished by using a variety of quantification strategies and approaches, as well as observations on their widespread application as a research approach in several academic fields.

Research Locale

Quezon province is in the Southern tip of CALABARZON region in Luzon. Its capital is the city of Lucena. The province was named after Manuel L. Quezon.

This study was conducted in the Third Congressional District of Quezon Province, comprised of 12 municipalities, 213 elementary schools, and 50 secondary schools. The researcher chose this locale primarily to address the needs of the teachers for development, and to determine which generation of teachers are well motivated to develop professionally.

Research Population and Sample

In choosing the population and sample, the researcher would apply purposive sampling, where the researcher relies on judgment when choosing members of the population. The population was the selected teachers from different schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon. The respondents of this research comprised of 204 teachers, wherein 17 teachers were selected from different generations from the 12 towns.

Research Instrument

The researcher employed a self-made survey questionnaire in this study to determine the profile of the respondents as to generations (generation z, generation y, generation x, and baby boomers; the data on the motivational level of respondents per generation were gathered from the areas of content focus, active learning, collaboration, models and modelling, coaching and expert support, feedback and reflection and sustained duration. for the validity of the instrument, the researcher conducted a pilot testing among 30 teachers classified according to the generations they belong to, wherein six (6) teacher respondents were coming from generation z, nine (9) teacher respondents from the millennial generation, nine (9) teacher respondents from generation x, and lastly, six (6) teacher respondents from the baby boomers generation.

Data Gathering Procedure

In conducting the data gathering, the researcher wrote a letter of request for the Schools Division Superintendent for the approval of the distribution of survey questionnaires to ensure utmost cooperation from the target respondents. The distribution was personally conducted by the researcher, as well as the retrieval. After the retrieval, the questionnaires were generated. The statistician would help the researcher in the statistical treatment and data analysis.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data gathered through the questionnaire were classified, tabulated, and analyzed. These were treated with the frequency distribution, weighted mean, and rank order. The data that answered the specific problems were as follows:

The assessment for the respondent's profile was determined through Percentage and Frequency Distribution.

To determine the level of motivation of teachers for different tasks as bases for professional development, the scale below was used for the analysis of the data to be collected.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

The study confined to the level of teacher's motivation towards professional development. It is delimited with teachers who are belong to millennials, X, Y, and Baby Boomers' generation. The population of the study was the selected teachers from different schools in the Third Congressional District of Quezon. The respondents of this research comprised of 204 teachers wherein 17 teachers were selected from different generations of the 12 towns. The collected data were the profile of the respondents as to generations: Generation Z or iGen (1997- 2010); Generation Y (Millennials) (1981- 1996); Generation X (1965- 1980); Baby Boomers (1946- 1964). The motivational level of teachers towards professional development across generations (Generation Z or iGen, Generation Y (millennials), Generation X and Baby Boomers) in terms of: Content Focused; Active Learning; Task Collaboration; Effective Practices; Learning Support; Reflective Outlook and Sustainable Plan. It also determined if there is a significant difference in the level of motivation towards professional development of the generations (Generation Z or Gen Z, (millennials) Generation Y, Generation X, and Baby Boomers) and created a program intervention that could be proposed to motivate teachers to upgrade themselves toward professional development.

RESULTS

Part I. Profile of the Respondents

Table 2.

Distribution of the Respondents According to Generations

Generations	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Generation Z (Gen Z) 1997-2010	36	17.65
Generation Y (Millennials) 1981 – 1996	60	29.41
Generation X 1965-1980	60	29.41
Baby Boomers 1946-1964	48	23.53
Total	204	100.00

Part II. Level of Teachers' Motivation Towards Professional Development Across Generations

Table 3.

Level of Teachers' Motivation Towards Professional Development Across Generations in terms of Content Focus

Factors	Gen Z	VD	Gen Y	VD	Gen X	VD	Baby Boomers	VD	Overall Mean	Verbal Description
Teachers applied different strategies in teaching.	4.06	WM	4.12	WM	4.02	WM	3.77	WM	4.00	Well-Motivated
The teacher assures to associate teaching strategies to curriculum.	4.11	WM	4.18	WM	4.00	WM	3.81	WM	4.03	Well-Motivated
Teachers include the application of ICT	3.94	WM	4.17	WM	3.85	WM	3.17	WM	3.80	Well-Motivated
Teachers develops materials for different instructional	4.25	WM	4.15	WM	4.02	WM	3.73	WM	4.03	Well-Motivated
Teachers applied varied assessment tools	4.19	WM	4.08	WM	3.97	WM	3.83	WM	4.01	Well-Motivated
Grand Mean	4.11	WM	4.14	WM	3.97	WM	3.66	WM	3.97	Well-Motivated

Table 4.

Level of Teachers' Motivation Towards Professional Development Across Generations in terms of Active Learning

Factors	Gen Z	VD	Gen Y	VD	Gen X	VD	Baby Boomers	VD	Overall Mean	Verbal Description
Hands-on experience in designing new teaching strategies.	4.17	WM	4.13	WM	4.03	WM	3.90	WM	4.05	Well-Motivated
New teaching style in enhancing the active participation of learners.	4.22	WM	4.13	WM	4.03	WM	3.94	WM	4.07	Well-Motivated
Apply real-life situations in the teaching and learning process.	4.25	WM	4.28	WM	4.10	WM	4.06	WM	4.17	Well-Motivated
Texts to identify potential literacy challenges to learners	4.11	WM	4.12	WM	4.08	WM	3.94	WM	4.06	Well-Motivated
Classroom routines regularly.	4.08	WM	4.32	WM	4.12	WM	3.98	WM	4.14	Well-Motivated
Grand Mean:	4.17	WM	4.20	WM	4.07	WM	3.96	WM	4.10	Well-Motivated

Table 5.

Level of Teachers' Motivation Towards Professional Development Across Generations in terms of Task Collaboration

Factors	Gen Z	VD	Gen Y	VD	Gen X	VD	Baby Boomers	VD	Overall Mean	Verbal Description
Shares and collaborates	4.17	WM	4.18	WM	4.08	WM	3.90	WM	4.08	Well-Motivated
Environment that is positively cooperative.	4.14	WM	4.33	WM	4.10	WM	3.98	WM	4.15	Well-Motivated
Promotes an inquiry-based approach to teaching.	4.08	WM	4.22	WM	3.95	WM	3.85	WM	4.03	Well-Motivated
Workshops and enjoys working with others.	4.17	WM	4.20	WM	4.12	WM	3.85	WM	4.09	Well-Motivated
Collaboration among colleagues within school and with other institutions.	4.11	WM	4.28	WM	4.05	WM	3.83	WM	4.08	Well-Motivated
Grand Mean	4.13	WM	4.24	WM	4.06	WM	3.88	WM	4.09	Well-Motivated

Table 6.

Level of Teachers' Motivation Towards Professional Development Across Generations in terms of Effective Practices

Factors	Gen Z	VD	Gen Y	VD	Gen X	VD	Baby Boomers	VD	Overall Mean	Verbal Description
Models on lesson plans, unit plans, and sample student work.	4.00	WM	4.25	WM	3.97	WM	3.77	WM	4.01	Well-Motivated
Peer teaching observations.	4.03	WM	4.08	WM	4.05	WM	3.85	WM	4.01	Well-Motivated
Accomplished teaching.	3.94	WM	4.08	WM	3.92	WM	3.77	WM	3.94	Well-Motivated
Demonstration teaching based on educational principles and practices.	4.00	WM	4.23	WM	4.02	WM	3.88	WM	4.04	Well-Motivated
Uses and provides curriculum materials for teaching.	4.03	WM	4.15	WM	4.02	WM	3.85	WM	4.02	Well-Motivated
Grand Mean	4.00	WM	4.16	WM	3.99	WM	3.83	WM	4.00	Well-Motivated

Table 7.

Level of Teachers' Motivation Towards Professional Development Across Generations in terms of Learning Support

Factors	Gen Z	VD	Gen Y	VD	Gen X	VD	Baby Boomers	VD	Overall Mean	Verbal Description
Monitors learners' progress.	4.08	WM	4.30	WM	4.02	WM	3.83	WM	4.07	Well-Motivated
A culture of high expectations in support of the learners.	4.14	WM	4.13	WM	4.10	WM	3.75	WM	4.03	Well-Motivated
Address learners' learning needs.	4.25	WM	4.17	WM	4.10	WM	3.85	WM	4.09	Well-Motivated
Localize learning materials for effective teaching and learning process.	4.14	WM	4.17	WM	3.98	WM	3.81	WM	4.02	Well-Motivated
Use of school resources to meet the priorities outlined toward learners' progress.	4.00	WM	4.10	WM	3.90	WM	3.77	WM	3.95	Well-Motivated
Grand Mean:	4.12	WM	4.17	WM	4.02	WM	3.80	WM	4.03	Well-Motivated

Table 8.

Level of Teachers' Motivation Towards Professional Development Across Generations in terms of Reflective Outlook

Factors	Gen Z	VD	Gen Y	VD	Gen X	VD	Baby Boomers	VD	Overall Mean	Verbal Description
Daily Experiences	4.08	WM	4.20	WM	4.05	WM	3.73	WM	4.02	Well-Motivated
Issues and problems and teaches in a reflective way	4.11	WM	4.15	WM	4.03	WM	3.77	WM	4.02	Well-Motivated
Utilizes good values, beliefs and attitudes while on duty	4.03	WM	4.19	WM	3.98	WM	3.79	WM	4.00	Well-Motivated
Community activities voluntarily	3.92	WM	4.12	WM	3.90	WM	3.77	WM	3.94	Well-Motivated
Professional discretion to avoid scandal, gossip, and any preferential treatment for the learner	4.08	WM	4.25	WM	3.92	WM	3.88	WM	4.03	Well-Motivated
Grand Mean:	4.04	WM	4.18	WM	3.98	WM	3.79	WM	4.00	Well-Motivated

Table 9.

Level of Teachers' Motivation Towards Professional Development Across Generations in terms of Sustainable Plan

Factors	Gen Z	VD	Gen Y	VD	Gen X	VD	Baby Boomers	VD	Overall Mean	Verbal Description
Advanced educational degree to gain a fresh prospective	4.03	WM	3.97	WM	3.87	WM	3.71	WM	3.89	Well-Motivated
Accepts advice, criticism, and evaluation from administrators	4.00	WM	4.08	WM	3.77	WM	3.63	WM	3.87	Well-Motivated
Attends professional workshops, trainings, and seminars	3.92	WM	4.10	WM	3.87	WM	3.56	WM	3.87	Well-Motivated
Engages in social media as best practices among teachers.	3.89	WM	4.02	WM	3.58	WM	3.27	WM	3.69	Well-Motivated
Action research that will give sustainable solution to the problems encountered in teaching and learning process	3.61	WM	3.80	WM	3.42	WM	3.21	WM	3.51	Well-Motivated
Grand Mean	3.89	WM	3.99	WM	3.70	WM	3.48	WM	3.77	Well-Motivated

PART III. Test for Significant Difference on the Level of Motivation Towards Professional Development of the Generations (Generation Z, Generation Y, Generation X, And Baby Boomers)

Table 10.

Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Comparison of the Level of Motivation Towards Professional Development of the Generations (Generation Z, Generation Y, Generation X, Baby Boomers)

Indicators	Generation	Mean Rank	K-statistic	p-value	Decision	Remarks
Content Focus	Generation Z	118.79	27.226	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	Generation Y	120.11				
	Generation X	104.07				
	Baby Boomers	66.31				
Active Learning	Generation Z	108.08	7.900	0.048	Reject Ho	Significant
	Generation Y	115.62				
	Generation X	99.38				
	Baby Boomers	85.81				
Task Collaboration	Generation Z	106.54	11.493	0.009	Reject Ho	Significant
	Generation Y	119.01				
	Generation X	99.79				
	Baby Boomers	82.22				
Effective Practices	Generation Z	99.90	11.500	0.009	Reject Ho	Significant
	Generation Y	120.84				
	Generation X	100.78				

	Generations	Mean	F	p-value	Decision	Significance
Learning Support	Baby Boomers	83.67	12.676	0.005	Reject Ho	Significant
	Generation Z	108.90				
	Generation Y	118.08				
	Generation X	101.70				
Reflective Outlook	Baby Boomers	79.22	15.387	0.002	Reject Ho	Significant
	Generation Z	109.33				
	Generation Y	121.07				
	Generation X	98.86				
Sustainable Plan	Baby Boomers	78.72	23.063	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
	Generation Z	113.82				
	Generation Y	125.28				
	Generation X	96.26				
	Baby Boomers	73.34				

Note: "If the p- value is less than or equal to the level of significance (0.05), reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 11.

Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test in Determining Significant Difference in the Level of Motivation Towards Professional Development of the Generations

Generations	Content Focus		Active Learning	
	p-value	Remarks	p-value	Remarks
Generation Z vs. Generation Y	0.914	Not Significant	0.529	Not Significant
Generation Z vs. Generation X	0.227	Not Significant	0.467	Not Significant
Generation Z vs. Baby Boomers	0.000	Significant	0.075	Not Significant
Generation Y vs. Generation X	0.129	Not Significant	0.117	Not Significant
Generation Y vs. Baby Boomers	0.000	Significant	0.007	Significant
Generation X vs. Baby Boomers	0.001	Significant	0.216	Not Significant

Note: "If the p- value is less than or equal to the Bonferroni Correction (0.05/6 =0.0083), reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 12.

Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test in Determining the Significant Difference in the Level of Motivation Towards Professional Development of the Generations

Generations	Task Collaboration		Effective Practices	
	p-value	Remarks	p-value	Remarks
Generation Z vs. Generation Y	0.298	Not Significant	0.083	Not Significant
Generation Z vs. Generation X	0.573	Not Significant	0.942	Not Significant
Generation Z vs. Baby Boomers	0.052	Not Significant	0.198	Not Significant
Generation Y vs. Generation X	0.064	Not Significant	0.055	Not Significant
Generation Y vs. Baby Boomers	0.001	Significant	0.001	Significant
Generation X vs. Baby Boomers	0.110	Not Significant	0.122	Not Significant

Note: "If the p- value is less than or equal to the Bonferroni Correction (0.05/6 =0.0083), reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 13.

Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test in Determining the Significant Difference in the Level of Motivation Towards Professional Development of the Generations

Generations	Learning Support		Reflective Outlook	
	p-value	Remarks	p-value	Remarks
Generation Z vs. Generation Y	0.450	Not Significant	0.330	Not Significant
Generation Z vs. Generation X	0.553	Not Significant	0.385	Not Significant
Generation Z vs. Baby Boomers	0.019	Not Significant	0.015	Not Significant
Generation Y vs. Generation X	0.119	Not Significant	0.033	Not Significant
Generation Y vs. Baby Boomers	0.000	Significant	0.000	Significant
Generation X vs. Baby Boomers	0.044	Not Significant	0.069	Not Significant

Note: "If the p- value is less than or equal to the Bonferroni Correction (0.05/6 =0.0083), reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 14.

Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test in Determining the Significant Difference in the Level of Motivation Towards Professional Development of the Generations

Generations	Sustainable Plan	
	p-value	Remarks
Generation Z vs. Generation Y	0.353	Not Significant
Generation Z vs. Generation X	0.154	Not Significant
Generation Z vs. Baby Boomers	0.002	Significant
Generation Y vs. Generation X	0.007	Significant
Generation Y vs. Baby Boomers	0.000	Significant
Generation X vs. Baby Boomers	0.043	Not Significant

Note: "If the p- value is less than or equal to the Bonferroni Correction (0.05/6 =0.0083), reject Ho, otherwise failed to reject Ho."

Table 15.

Test of Normality using Shapiro Wilk W-Test

Variable	Sample Size	p-value	Remarks
Level of Teachers' Motivation towards Professional Development across Generations	204	0.001	Not Normal

Note: "If the p- value is greater than or equal to the significance level (0.05) NORMAL, otherwise NOT NORMAL."

PART IV. Program Intervention to Motivate Teachers to Upgrade Toward Professional Development

Continuous professional development (CPD) helps teachers improve their understanding of how to deliver effective education, and ensures they can adapt to the changing needs of students.

However, at a time when many teachers are under pressure, and when the development needs of each teacher can vary substantially, it can be hard to understand how best to provide a professional development service for teachers. This intervention program can help create development plans for teachers.

DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

Table 2 presents the distribution of the respondents according to generations. As can be seen from the table, most of the respondents were from Generation X 1965-1980 and Generation Y (Millennials) 1981-1996 with 29.41 % or, with a frequency of 60. It implies that most of the respondents are experienced educators. They have in-depth knowledge and more expertise in their fields.

This finding aligns with (Polat et al.,2019) that teachers in this generation are more dedicated to teaching as a profession, a civic responsibility, and a reflection of their ideals. They may have a greater love for working long hours because of their level of devotion to both their personal and professional lives.

However, only 23.53% were from baby boomers, and the lowest among the ranks comes from the new generation, Generation Z, with 17.65% because the present generation has just began their service while the baby boomers are declining the numbers.

Part II. Level of Teachers' Motivation Towards Professional Development Across Generations

Table 3.

Level of Teachers' Motivation Towards Professional Development Across Generations in terms of Content Focus

Table 3 presents the level of teachers' motivation towards content focus. Based on the data shown, the level of teachers' motivation was high, with a 3.97 grand mean. It implies that teachers identified the most needed for learners that focus on learning, such as strategies, training, and techniques.

Among all the statements, the statements "teachers apply teaching strategies associated with teaching strategies curricula" and "develop different materials for instructions varied for the teaching and learning process" with 4.03 mean respectively, which signify that they teachers are Well Motivated in these indicators. It is followed by the use of assessment tools with a 4.01 mean, while the applied strategies in teaching that has a 4.0 mean, which also means they are well motivated. Though the indicator

pertaining to teachers' application of ICT has the lowest mean of 3.80, it is still interpreted that they are well motivated.

The move to a 21st-century education is demanded among the teachers, however there is a divide between those who look at 21st-century education and preparing children for the digital world and educators who cling to the conventional image of schools (Yarrington, as cited by (Henebery, 2015).

Aligned with that and considering the present technology and the digital world than previous generations, experts emphasize that members of Generation Z are capable of thriving in both virtual and real environments. They see these two worlds as complementary to one other, thus they can move between them with ease (Chomałowska, Żarczyńska-Dobiesz, 2014).

Table 4.

Level of Teachers' Motivation Towards Professional Development Across Generations in terms of Active Learning

Table 4 reveals the mean scores of the level of teachers' motivation towards professional development across generations in terms of active learning. As can be seen from the table, the level of teachers' motivation in active learning has a 4.10 mean which implies that teachers are well motivated. It suggests that in terms of active learning, teachers consistently practice eagerness in exploring different pedagogical tasks.

The respondents believed that using real-life situations in the teaching and learning process with 4.17 mean, practicing classroom routines regularly with a mean of 4.14, creates a new teaching style in enhancing the active participation of learners (4.07), analyzes texts to identify potential literacy challenges to learners (4.06), and get hands-on experience in designing new teaching strategies (4.05) which makes them well motivated in these indicators.

Generally, the teachers, no matter what generation they are from, are all active in participating, especially in learning different processes, classroom routines, and teaching styles in the classroom. According to (Cox,2023), using real-world examples and tackling real-world problems in the classroom can make learning more meaningful to students. Moreover, it can help spark excitement in gaining knowledge about important issues.

Table 5.

Level of Teachers' Motivation Towards Professional Development Across Generations in terms of Task Collaboration

Table 5 shows the mean scores of the level of teachers' motivation towards professional development across generations in terms of task collaboration. As can be seen from the table, the level of teachers' motivation in active learning garnered an overall mean of 4.09 which also means that they are well-motivated in this component of professional development. It implies that in terms of collaboration, teachers are eager to

participate in tasks that involve cooperation with fellow teachers. Moreover, the respondents are found to be well motivated in creating an environment that is positively cooperative as evidenced by the mean of 4.15, participates in collaborative workshops and enjoys working with others with 4.09 mean, shares ideas and collaborates with colleagues, and promotes collaboration among colleagues within school and with other institutions with 4.07 mean, respectively.

Based on the results, teachers are well-motivated in assuring that they are part of a collaborative environment. It is a positive response that teachers create a collaborative environment for the quality education of the learners.

This finding is supported by (Ahmed,2019) who emphasized that collaborative learning is a method of education in which a group of students (two or more) attempts to learn something together using group projects, assignments, etc. In this type of learning, students learn from others' skills and resources. Collaborative learning is an educational approach to teaching and learning in which groups of students participate in solving issues, completing tasks, or creating products together.

Table 6.

Level of Teachers' Motivation Towards Professional Development Across Generations in terms of Effective Practices

Table 6 presents the mean scores of the level of teachers' motivation towards professional development across generations in terms of effective practices. As can be seen from the table, the respondents claimed that in terms of effective practices, they are well motivated to ensure effective practices for teaching and learning as evidenced by a grand mean of 4.0. Specifically, they claimed that they primarily practice demonstration teaching based on educational principles and practices (4.04), and they also use and provide curriculum (4.02).

Further, they also claim that view models include lesson plans, unit plans, sample student work, and Practice peer teaching observations (4.01). It only implies that teachers effectively practice by following the principles of teaching.

(Ahmed,2019) stated that designing and developing instruction that is effective, consistent, and meaningful can be achieved by following principles for good practice.

Table 7

Level of Teachers' Motivation Towards Professional Development Across Generations in terms of Learning Support

Table 7 shows the mean scores of the level of teachers' motivation towards professional development across generations in terms of learning support. As viewed in the table, it reveals that teachers are well-motivated in terms of learning support, with a 4.03 grand mean. It only implies that different generations claimed that they are well-motivated in giving learning support.

The respondents claimed that they are mostly focused on addressing learners' learning needs (4.09), that they are systematically monitoring learners' progress (4.07), and they are establishing and sustaining a culture of high expectations in support of the learners (4.03).

As learning support teachers engage students in the use of technology, explore, and participate in collaborative groups, interact with others, and make connections to real world experiences. They are also encouraged to use technology as instructional method in teaching (Lisenbee, 2016).

Further, according to (Hodges.2016), educators are transforming the workplace from an environment as learning support managers utilized force and control to manage staff to one that is more collaborative and team-oriented, with coaches assisting staff members in reaching their objectives. In order to bring about change, this new generation requires mentors to bounce ideas off of and to be regarded as valuable partners.

Table 8.

Level of Teachers' Motivation Towards Professional Development Across Generations in terms of Reflective Outlook

Table 8 presents the mean scores of the level of teachers' motivation towards professional development across generations in terms of reflective outlook. Overall, as can be seen from the table, the respondents claimed that they are well-motivated in reflective outlook across different generations as evidenced by a grand mean of 4.0.

Based on the responses, the teachers are well motivated when they exercise utmost professional discretion to avoid scandal, gossip, and any preferential treatment for the learner (4.03); building a reflective bridge between students and the book's content to whatever they are experiencing daily, and they address issues and problems and teaches reflectively both obtained a mean of 4.02.

These findings find support in Corwin press, who stated that one of the best methods for professionals of all generations to collaborate is to build a pleasant workplace, as stated in the book by (Abram & Von Frank,2013). Knowing exactly what has to be done and who is in charge of each task, no matter how big or small, is a necessary step on the road to success.

It only implies that a reflective outlook was highly practiced among teachers. They avoid improper actions and maintain reflection, as they also address different issues and problems.

According to the Code of Ethics of the Philippines, Section 1. A teacher is, above all, a human being endowed with life for which it is the highest obligation to always live with dignity, whether in school, in the home, or elsewhere section 2. A teacher should place a premium upon self-discipline as the primary principle of personal behavior in all relationships with others and in all situations section 3. A teacher shall continuously

maintain a dignified personality that could serve as a model worthy of emulation by learners, peers, and all others.

Table 9.

Level of Teachers' Motivation Towards Professional Development Across Generations in terms of Sustainable Plan

Table 9 shows the mean scores of the level of teachers' motivation towards professional development across generations in terms of sustainable plans. Overall, the respondents' responses claimed they are well motivated in sustainable plans. It implies that along with different generations, they all have the same response, as well as motivation in their assuring to have a sustainable plan for the school's development.

Most respondents agreed to take up an advanced educational degree to gain a fresh perspective, with a 3.89 mean. Then, followed by the statement, accept advice, criticism, and evaluation from administrators and attend professional workshops, training, and seminars, having a 3.87 mean.

According to (Washington,2019), professional development (PD) in the 21st century is vital to the growth and development of contemporary educators. Today's educational realm contains multiple perspectives, technologies, and opportunities for students and educational leaders. The goal of professional development for educators is to go beyond maintenance and to create sustainability and professional longevity.

PART III. Test for Significant Difference on the Level of Motivation Towards Professional Development of the Generations (Generation Z, Generation Y, Generation X, And Baby Boomers)

Table 10.

Kruskal Wallis H-Test: Comparison of the Level of Motivation Towards Professional Development of the Generations (Generation Z, Generation Y, Generation X, Baby Boomers)

The table above shows the Kruskal Wallis H-Test for the comparison of the level of motivation towards professional development of the generations (Generation Z, Generation Y, Generation X, Baby Boomers) as revealed by the respondents. It shows that in terms of content focus with 0.000 p-values, active learning with 0.048, task collaboration with 0.009 p-values, effective practices with 0.009, learning support with 0.005, reflective outlook 0.002, and sustainable plan with 0.000 all obtained significant. It only implies a significant difference in the Level of Motivation Towards Professional Development. They conclude that they have different perceptions of professional development since some are aging, new, and eager for development and promotion.

These findings find support in (Yaakob et al.,2020) said that the school organization consists of a multi-generation teacher community, which would mean professional development programs of one-size-fits-all should change towards fulfilling

the needs of all teachers to strengthen the quality of education. It is because each generation has different ways of accepting changes since teachers from different generations have various acceptance of professional development.

Table 11.

Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test in Determining Significant Difference in the Level of Motivation Towards Professional Development of the Generations

Table 11 shows the Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to determine the significant difference in the level of motivation towards professional development of the generations (Generation Z, Generation Y, Generation X, and Baby Boomers). As shown in the table, in terms of content focus, there is only a significant difference between Generation Z vs. Baby Boomers (p value=0.000), Generation Y vs. Baby Boomers (p value= 0.000), and Generation X vs. Baby Boomers (p value=0.001). It may imply that Baby boomers have different perceptions in terms of professional development when compared to other generations of teachers which may be due to their attitude towards work since they are mainly at the age nearing retirement.

However, in terms of active learning, it is remarkably shown that in all generations, there is no significant difference in the active learning practices. As shown, Generation Z vs. Generation Y (p value=0.529), Generation Z vs. Generation X (p value=0.467), Generation Z vs. Baby Boomers (p value=0.075), Generation Y vs. Generation X (0.117), Generation Y vs. Baby Boomers (0.007) and Generation X vs. Baby Boomers (0.216). They dive deeper into the material with their teachers and peers before internalizing it and relating it to real-world experiences. Active learners participate in interactive discussions and activities related to the material and engage in quality study time – often using various study styles to absorb the information.

Table 12.

Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test in Determining the Significant Difference in the Level of Motivation Towards Professional Development of the Generations

Table 12 presents the Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test to determine the significant difference in the level of motivation towards professional development of the generations (Generation Z, Generation Y, Generation X, and Baby Boomers). As revealed by the data above, it shows a significant difference in task collaboration and effective practices among Generation Y vs Baby Boomers, with 0.001 for task collaboration and 0.001 for effective practices. It can be inferred that only the two early generations have differences in practicing their task collaboration and effective practices.

Meanwhile, the statement that millennials are sometimes stereotyped and overly dependent may be due to a misunderstanding of this generation of professionals. Many who have worked with them know there is another side to their story. Many young people are highly achieving, tenacious, confident, and progressive educators. They are often high-energy multi-taskers who are deeply tech-savvy and globally minded (Abrams, 2018). Millennial teachers can bring enthusiasm, tech readiness, competence, and

collaboration into the workplace. Many of them are accustomed to working in teams and enjoy having support and structure.

Table 13.

Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test in Determining the Significant Difference in the Level of Motivation Towards Professional Development of the Generations

Table 13 presents the Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test in determining the significant difference in the level of motivation towards professional development of the generations (Generation Z, Generation Y, Generation X, and Baby Boomers). As viewed from the data in the table, it can be inferred that in terms of learning support, Generation Y and Baby Boomers have significant differences, with the reflective to outlook with both 0.000 p values, respectively.

The data above implies that Generation Y and Z differ in how they handle their learning support to their learners and how they effectively look at their work. (Eulberg,2019) said that millennials, who have been taught the importance of balancing their careers with their personal lives- find this mindset less appreciated and practiced in education and struggle to reconcile their beliefs about self-care with the demands of being a teacher. Millennial teachers may face challenges today, but these professionals are the future of education (Eulberg, 2019).

In addition, they expect a comprehensive induction system that includes extensive training, sources, and supplies. Like many generations in the past, millennials can be quick to analyze their elders' shortcomings (Barker, 2015).

Table 14.

Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test in Determining the Significant Difference in the Level of Motivation Towards Professional Development of the Generations

Table 14 reveals the Dunn Post Ad Hoc Test in determining the significant difference in the level of motivation towards professional development of the generations (Generation Z, Generation Y, Generation X, and Baby Boomers). As revealed by the data above, it shows that in terms of the motivation towards professional development in maintaining sustainable development. It shows that Generation Z vs. Baby Boomers (0.002), Generation Y vs. Generation X (0.007), and Generation Y vs. Baby Boomers (0.000).

These findings imply that the motivation of teachers in making sustainable plans do not differ except when Gen Y and Gen Z are being compared because prospecting plans and the outlook of the younger teachers towards changes and development might differ from the perspective of seasoned teachers.

Sustainable development is becoming more and more implemented with each generation. Finally, in-house living in everyday situations can make a change towards sustainability happen with students and learners, but the other way is possible. Considering this, learning in a group in an everyday situation might be a new approach

for teacher training in Education for Sustainable Development. Teachers from different generations might have different perspectives (Hepper, 2018).

Table 15.

Test of Normality using Shapiro Wilk W-Test

Table 15 shows the test of normality using the Shapiro-Wilk W-Test conducted on the level of teachers' motivation towards professional development across generations. As can be seen from the table, the p-value of the variable obtained 0.001, which is not usual. It may imply that the level of motivation among the different generations shows different levels variances. It may mean that since they were in different generations, they might have different perspectives towards their work, especially on their motivation towards their professional development.

These findings may be related to the findings of (Galloway,2013) that many millennials are eager and ready for new learning and opportunities sooner rather than later. In education, however, states and districts often require teachers to have at least three, if not five or seven years in the profession before taking on formal leadership roles. The process may be even slower in individual schools. These restrictions may not sit well with younger teachers who want to take on leadership responsibilities or explore new roles, especially if they see their peers in other professions being promoted sooner and more often.

However, as stated in the book of (Abram Von Frank and Corwin,2013), the best ways for professionals of all generations to work together to create a harmonious workplace. Part of the path to success knows exactly what needs to be done and who is responsible for each task- small or big.

PART IV. Program Intervention to Motivate Teachers to Upgrade Toward Professional Development

Continuous professional development (CPD) helps teachers improve their understanding of how to deliver effective education, and ensures they can adapt to the changing needs of students.

However, at a time when many teachers are under pressure, and when the development needs of each teacher can vary substantially, it can be hard to understand how best to provide a professional development service for teachers. This intervention program can help create development plans for teachers.

Summary of Findings

This part presents the summary of findings to provide a gist of the significant results of the study.

1. Profile of the Respondents

In terms of the Profile of the Respondents, most of the respondents were from Generation X 1965-1980 and Generation Y (millennials) 1981-1996.

2. Motivational Level of Teachers Towards Professional Development Across Generations (Generation Z or iGen, Generation Y (millennials), Generation X and Baby Boomers).

2.1 In terms of teacher's motivation across generations as to Content Focus, a "well motivated" level is observed.

2.2 In terms of teacher's motivation across generations as to Active Learning, a "well motivated" level is observed.

2.3 In terms of teacher's motivation across generations as to Task Collaboration, a "well motivated" level is observed.

2.4 In terms of teacher's motivation across generations as to Effective Practice, a "well motivated" level is observed.

2.5 In terms of teacher's motivation across generations as to Learning Support, a "well motivated" level is observed.

2.6 In terms of teacher's motivation across generations as to Reflective Outlook, a "well motivated" level is observed.

2.7 In terms of teacher's motivation across generations as to Sustainable Plan, a "well motivated" level is observed.

3. Significant Difference in the Level of Motivation towards Professional Development of the Generations (Generation Z or Gen Z (millennials), Generation Y, and Generation X, and Baby Boomers)

3.1 There is no significant difference between Generation Z and Y, Generation Z and X and Generation Y and X while there is significant difference between Generation Z and Baby Boomers, Generation Y and Baby Boomers, and Generation X and Baby Boomers in terms of Content Focused and Active Learning.

3.2 There is no significant difference between Generation Z and Y, Generation Z and X, and Generation Z and X, Generation Z and Baby Boomers, Generation Y and X, and Generation X and Baby Boomers while there is significant difference between Generation Y and Baby Boomers in terms of Task Collaboration and Effective Practices.

3.3 There is no significant difference between Generation Z and Y, Generation Z and X, Generation Z and Baby Boomers, Generation Y and X and Generation Y and Baby Boomers while there is significant difference between Generation Y and Baby Boomers in terms of Learning Support and Reflective Outlook.

3.4 There is no significant difference between Generation Z and Y, Generation Z and X, and Generation X and Baby Boomers while there is significant difference between Generation Z and Baby Boomers, Generation Y and X, and Generation Y and Baby Boomers in terms of Sustainable Plan.

4. A program intervention was proposed to motivate teachers to upgrade themselves toward professional development.
-

Conclusions

Based on the findings as summarized, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Teachers were from Generation X 1965-1980 and Generation Y (millennials).
 2. The level of teachers' motivation across generations in Content-Focus, Active Learning, Task Collaboration, Effective Practices, Learning Support, Reflective Outlook, and Sustainable Plan were all well-motivated.
 3. There is a significant difference in the level of motivation towards professional development of the generations with Generation Z vs. Baby Boomers and Generation Y vs. Baby Boomers therefore the hypothesis is rejected.
 4. The researcher proposed a program intervention to motivate teachers to upgrade themselves toward professional development.
-

Recommendations

The researcher recommends the following:

1. Since most of the respondents are middle-aged, teachers may continue to further improve their skills through different trainings and activities for the school such as Trend on new technology applications and workshop on materials and teaching tools.
2. Due to the findings that teachers are well-motivated across generations, teachers may intensify their level of motivation to be very well-motivated through continuous growth by means of engaging in different workshop. They may also consider helping the school for the development and improvement of the learners through providing them monitoring, encouragement, and continuing professional development.
3. Since that generation, older and younger generations have contrasting views on professional development in some areas. School heads may consider to host events where various generations are grouped together to discuss differing viewpoints. School heads may also continue to provide technical assistance to assist older generations.
4. The crafted intervention program may be utilized to reach the highest level of teachers' motivation toward professional development and contribute to their productivity for the learners and the schools.

5. Future researchers may conduct similar studies in other schools and consider the areas not covered and discussed in the study.
-

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In this study, ethical considerations were considered by the researcher. The participants remained anonymous throughout the study even to the researchers themselves. There will be no identifying information about the participants. Further, all the data were kept confidential. Participants were assured that identifying information will not be made available to anyone who is not directly involved in the study. Ethical considerations are form a major element in research.

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